

Students' Perception of Spanking as a Disciplinary Technique

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Abstract:

There has been controversy regarding the use of spanking in controlling students' misbehaviours. Against the variations in opinions is this study executed to investigate the perception of students on the influence of spanking in controlling their misbehaviours in public secondary schools in Anambra State. One research question guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and was carried out in Onitsha South Local Government Area of the State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select a target study sample of 109 out of the 1087 Junior Secondary School (2) students in the 6 public secondary schools in

Onitsha South Local Government Area of the state. A 10-item questionnaire designed by the researchers was used to elicit responses from the respondents, it was face validated by 5 experts. The instrument was reliability tested using Cronbach Alpha reliability method, yielding a co-efficient of 0.73 for internal consistency. Statistical means was used in answering the research question. The finding of the study revealed that spanking as perceived by the students positively influences the management of their misbehaviour. Based on the finding, it was recommended among other things that teachers should use spanking in controlling misbehavior but not in wrath but out of love to train up a child in the right way. Spanking should be used by teachers for controlling misbehavior provided that the principles guiding administration of it is duly followed.

Keywords: *Spanking, Secondary, Misbehaviours, School Behaviour Policy.*

Introduction

Managing students' behaviour is one of the vital roles of educational managers and a means of achieving educational goal. This is because no meaningful learning and school management exist in an environment where misbehavior thrives. The aim of school organization in any country is to achieve national educational goal, particularly, junior secondary education is factual in the Nigerian standard of educational system. It is that level of education children receive after primary school and before senior secondary

education. Junior secondary education is where children are groomed to have a diversified knowledge in intellectual, social, moral and emotional development. Among the specific objective of junior secondary education as specified by Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN,2013); include:

- a. to develop patriotic young people equipped to contribute to social development and performance of their civic responsibilities;

b. to inculcate values and raise morally upright individuals capable of independent thinking, and who appreciate the dignity of labour.

The above national educational objectives are suggestive that the onus of the junior secondary education was targeted at grooming students worthy in learning and character; therefore, behaviours management of students becomes imperative. Behaviour management in the school is concerned with ensuring that through teaching, coaching, mentoring and discipline that members of school organization do and act in a particular way that will promote and not hinder the educational goals of the school. In order to achieve this Ezenwangu (2022) stressed on the need to have school's behavior policy. According him, the purpose of school's behavior policy is to ensure that every member of the school community behave positively such that will make others feel valued and respected. Obviously, no school can strive optimally with negligence to misbehaviours. Misbehaviours are unacceptable way of doing or behaving that does not conform to the school regulations and hinders the educational objectives of the school. According to Nwankwo (2014) Students' misbehaviours also known as indiscipline among students is failure to adhere to rules and regulations meant to guide good conduct and behaviour necessary for effective learning in the school.

The expected school behaviours are embedded in the school rules and regulations which are readily made available from the inception of students' registration. The school behaviour policy contain the principles guiding administration of punishment, the accepted and unaccepted behaviours with the consequences of misbehavior are clearly stated. These behaviour policies are often articulated to students during orientation, school assembly and classroom exercises. Those who fail to adhere to the school behavior policy rules are usually faced with punishment. Among such punishment frequently used is spanking.

Spanking according to Donally and Stratus (2008) is defined as the use of physical force with the intention of causing a child to experience

pain but not injury for the purpose of controlling the child's behaviour. It is important to note that the aim of spanking at junior secondary school is usually to instill discipline and curb misbehavior before they escalates. Spanking seem operative at this level of education where the students are mainly teens whose temperamental dispositions seem hostile, thus more prone to misbehavior but when promptly discipline yield easily to positive behaviour. Also, students at this level of education are taught to accept punishment they deserve for misbehavior not to feel they cannot be punished or look for a way of escape for misbehaviour committed.

It is important to note that any form of misbehavior at junior secondary education is capable of disrupting the classroom learning by distracting not only the misbehaved child but others alike. Moreover, little students' misbehaviours seems little but when neglected is capable of being a threat to lives and properties of both students and staff. School managers are thus, expected to uphold discipline with all diligence as a shift from it increases chaos, bully, fight, stealing, lies, abuse, insult, cultism, drug use and misuse among student by extension pointers to social vices, blurred and frustrated future (Okeke-James, Igbokwe, Oguejiofor and Ogbuanya,2023).

Although, the use of spanking as a disciplinary technique to students' behaviours seems productive (Donally and Stratus,2008, Unachukwu and okeke-James,2017) many also seem to see it as counterproductive (Slade and Wissow,2004, Altschul, Lee and Gershoff 2016). Scholarly, spanking has been a controversial issue across scholars, individuals and nations. Thus, leaving many educational managers on the dilemma to go for or against spanking in the face of the persistence increase of unacceptable behaviours among junior secondary school students such as; stealing, disrespect to school staff, student-to student bully, cultism, vandalism of students and school properties. Thus, this inspired this study to empirically find out from the opinion of students the influence of spanking on the behaviours of students in

Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

Specifically, the study sought to determine the perception of students on the influence of spanking as discipline technique for misbehaviour in junior secondary school (2) students in Onitsha South Local Government Area.

Research Question

Do spanking as a disciplinary technique influence in controlling misbehaviours among the junior secondary school (2) students in Onitsha South Local Government Area.

Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey design, and study area was Anambra State. One research question guided the study. The population of the study comprised 1087 Junior Secondary School (2) students in public secondary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of

Anambra State, The sample of this study was 109 respondents. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample size. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled “Students’ Perception of the Influence of Spanking on Students’ Behaviour Questionnaire (SPISSQ)”. A 10-item questionnaire was structured on a four rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree(A), Disagree(D), Strongly Disagree(SD) weighted 4,3,2 and1 respectively. The face validation of the instrument was established by five experts in the Department of Educational Management and Policy from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The instrument was reliability tested using Cronbach Alpha reliability method, yielding a co-efficient of 0.73 for internal consistency. The researchers with the help of one research assistant collected data for the study. Statistical means was used in answering the research question. The mean response were adjudged on the basis of any mean score of 2.50 or above is taken to indicate agreement while any mean score that falls below 2.50 is taken as disagreement.

Result

Table 1. Mean Scores of Students on the Influence of Spanking in Controlling Students’ Misbehaviours

S/N	ITEMS	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	Total	Mean	Remark
1	Fear of being spanked encourages me to obey school rules and regulations	80 320	21 63	3 6	5 5	109 394	3.61	Agree
2	I choose to report to school prefects or teachers about offence of others to me instead of being spanked for fighting	57 228	35 105	5 10	12 12	109 355	3.3	Agree
3	Spanking reduces bully among students	60 240	22 66	14 28	13 13	109 347	3.2	Agree
4	Spanking reduces the rate to which students vandalize school properties	49 196	21 63	13 26	26 26	109 311	2.9	Agree
5	Fear of being spanked makes me to shun distraction in the classroom	59 236	26 78	11 22	13 13	109 349	3.2	Agree
6	Fear of being spanked restrain students from forming or joining gang in the school	59 236	28 84	7 14	15 15	109 349	3.2	Agree
7	Fear of being spanked makes me to pay attention during classroom exercise	60 240	24 72	14 28	11 11	109 351	3.2	Agree
8	Spanking reduces cult activities among students	64 256	14 42	12 24	19 19	109 341	3.1	Agree
9	Spanking reduces stealing among students	57 20	20 16	16 16	16 16	109	3.1	Agree

		228	60	32	16	336		
10	I choose to do my homework to avoid being spanked by my teachers	81 324	12 36	5 10	11 11	109 381	3.5	Agree
	Mean of Means						3.2	Agree

The result shown in table above revealed that students agreed on all the items. The mean of means value of 3.20 fall above 2.50 indicating agreement on influence of spanking in controlling misbehavior among junior secondary (2) students in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. This implies that spanking and fear of being spanked reduce misbehaviours among junior secondary school (2) students.

Discussion

The finding revealed that spanking can serve as deterrent and corrective for controlling misbehaviours. From the perception of students the fear of being spanked encourages them to obey school rules and regulations, they choose to report to school prefects or teachers about offence of others to them instead of being spanked for fighting, fear of being spanked makes them to pay attention during classroom exercise and students choose to do their homework to avoid being spanked by my teachers. This agrees with Kayode (2017) that disciplinary technique helps to promote orderliness while its negligence leads to bad conduct and wrong behaviours. Similarly, this finding is in tandem with Nwankwo (2014) who stated that punishment should be able to prevent offender and other people from committing the same offence in the future.

Moreover, from the perception of students spanking reduces; bullying among students, the rate to which students vandalize school, reduce cult activities among students and reduces stealing among students. This finding agrees with Ofoegbu (2017) who stated that punishment should make an offender a better person. Agreeably, Nwonkwo (2014) stated that school managers should place emphasis on the reformative dimension of punishment.

Conclusion

The finding of the study reveals that in the opinion of students that spanking as a disciplinary technique positively influence students' behaviours in junior secondary school.

Recommendations

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations have been made:

1. Teachers should use spanking not in wrath but out of love while controlling misbehavior.
2. Parents should be actively involved in the development and implementation of behavioral intervention plans for students who exhibit persistent misbehavior.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to uphold school discipline with diligence.
4. Awareness programs should be organized in schools to educate both parents and students to accept deserved punishment for unacceptable behaviours.

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